

Assessing Pregnancy Outcomes Based on Placenta Previa Location

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Abstract:

Background: Placenta previa, a condition where the placenta implants abnormally in the lower uterine segment, poses significant risks to both maternal and neonatal health. The location and type of placenta previa are crucial determinants of pregnancy outcomes, influencing the risk of hemorrhage, preterm birth, and the need for cesarean delivery. Despite advances in diagnostic techniques and management strategies, placenta previa remains a leading cause of obstetric morbidity.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate pregnancy outcomes based on the location of placenta previa among pregnant women at a government medical college.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted. A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa were included. The participants were categorized into four groups based on the type of placenta previa: complete, partial, marginal, and low-lying. Data on demographic characteristics, mode of delivery, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, Apgar scores, and maternal and neonatal complications were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Complete placenta previa was associated with the highest risk of adverse outcomes, including a 100% cesarean section rate, earlier gestational age at delivery (35.0 ± 2.0 weeks), and lower birth weight (2.6 ± 0.4 kg). Maternal complications, such as postpartum hemorrhage and the need for blood transfusions, were significantly more common in the complete placenta previa group. Neonatal complications, including preterm birth and low birth weight, were also more frequent in this group.

Conclusion: The location of placenta previa significantly impacts pregnancy outcomes, with complete placenta previa posing the highest risk for both maternal and neonatal complications. Early identification and careful monitoring of these cases are essential to mitigate risks.

Recommendations: Enhanced prenatal care, including frequent monitoring and timely intervention, is recommended for pregnancies complicated by complete placenta previa. Further research should focus on optimizing management strategies to improve outcomes in these high-risk cases.

Keywords: Placenta Previa, Pregnancy Outcomes, Maternal Complications, Neonatal Complications, Cesarean Section.

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Introduction

A serious obstetric issue known as placenta previa is defined by the placenta implanting abnormally in the lower uterine segment, covering the internal cervical os entirely or partially. It is a major contributor to perinatal problems such as low birth weight, premature delivery, and an increase in the need for caesarean sections. It also increases maternal morbidity. Recent years have seen an increase in the frequency of placenta previa, mostly as a result of rising rates of caesarean sections and older mothers, both of which are established risk factors for the illness. According to studies, placenta previa affects between 0.3% and 0.5% of pregnancies overall, with regional and population-based variations [1,2].

The kind and location of placenta previa are important factors in influencing the course of a pregnancy. Differentiating between entire, partial, marginal, and low-lying placenta previa is based on how much of the placenta covers the cervical os. Complete placenta previa, in which the placenta completely encloses the cervical os, is linked to the greatest risk of unfavourable consequences, such as severe haemorrhage in the mother, premature birth, and difficulties for the newborn [3]. The placenta's position with respect to the internal cervical os strongly affects the clinical care of the pregnancy and the delivery method; in order to avoid potentially fatal bleeding, caesarean sections are frequently required [4].

Understanding the pathophysiology of placenta previa and how it affects the outcomes of mothers and newborns has been the focus of recent research. Studies have demonstrated the significance of uterine scarring and anomalous placentation in the pathogenesis of placenta previa, underscoring the necessity of prompt diagnosis and vigilant observation during gestation [5]. Technological developments in ultrasonography have made it possible to diagnose placenta previa sooner and with more accuracy, which has improved care and birth preparation [6]. Nevertheless, despite these developments, there is still much to learn about the best way to treat placenta previa, especially in situations of full or anterior placenta previa. This study aimed to evaluate pregnancy outcomes based on the location of placenta previa among pregnant women at a government medical college.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Government Medical College, Purnia, Bihar, India, over a period of six months from March 2023 to August 2023.

Participants: The study included 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa during their pregnancy. These participants were recruited from the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of Government Medical College, Purnia.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa via ultrasound.
- Gestational age of at least 20 weeks at the time of diagnosis.
- Willingness to participate and provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with multiple pregnancies.
- Women with pre-existing medical conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, or any other chronic illness that could influence pregnancy outcomes.
- Women with previous uterine surgeries (e.g., cesarean section, myomectomy) that could confound results.

- Cases of placenta accreta or other placental abnormalities.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were recruited consecutively as they presented to the hospital and met the inclusion criteria. Information bias was minimized by using standardized data collection forms and procedures. Observer bias was controlled by having a single, blinded observer conduct the ultrasound evaluations and assess outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected using structured forms that included demographic information, clinical history, ultrasound findings regarding placenta previa location, and pregnancy outcomes such as mode of delivery, gestational age at delivery, neonatal outcomes, and maternal complications. Ultrasound findings were categorized into different types of placenta previa (complete, partial, marginal, and low-lying).

Procedure: Upon enrollment, participants underwent routine antenatal care, including regular ultrasound monitoring to assess the position of the placenta. Outcomes were recorded at delivery, including mode of delivery (vaginal or cesarean), gestational age, birth weight, Apgar scores, and any maternal or neonatal complications.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, and continuous variables as means and standard deviations. Associations between placenta previa location and pregnancy outcomes were examined using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 29.5 ± 4.3 years, with an age range of 21 to 39 years. The majority of the participants were multiparous (65%), and 35% were primiparous. The gestational age at diagnosis of placenta previa ranged from 20 to 36 weeks, with a mean gestational age of 28.2 ± 3.9 weeks.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Mean $\pm$ SD / n (%)
Age (years)	29.5 $\pm$ 4.3
Parity	
- Primiparous	35 (35%)
- Multiparous	65 (65%)
Gestational Age at Diagnosis (weeks)	28.2 $\pm$ 3.9

Types of Placenta Previa: Out of the 100 participants, 30% had complete placenta previa, 25% had partial placenta previa, 20% had marginal placenta previa, and 25% had a low-lying placenta.

Table 2: Distribution of Placenta Previa Types

Placenta Previa Type	n (%)
Complete	30 (30%)
Partial	25 (25%)
Marginal	20 (20%)
Low-lying	25 (25%)

Pregnancy Outcomes: The mode of delivery, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, and Apgar scores were analyzed across the different types of placenta previa.

- **Mode of Delivery:** Out of 100 participants, 78% delivered via cesarean section, while 22% had a vaginal delivery. Complete placenta previa had the highest rate of cesarean delivery (100%), followed by partial (84%), marginal (65%), and low-lying placenta (60%).
- **Gestational Age at Delivery:** The mean gestational age at delivery was 36.1 $\pm$ 2.4

weeks. Participants with complete placenta previa had the earliest mean delivery at 35.0 $\pm$ 2.0 weeks.

- **Birth Weight:** The mean birth weight was 2.9 $\pm$ 0.5 kg. Infants born to mothers with complete placenta previa had the lowest mean birth weight of 2.6 $\pm$ 0.4 kg.
- **Apgar Scores:** The 5-minute Apgar scores ranged from 6 to 10, with a mean score of 8.5 $\pm$ 1.2. Lower Apgar scores were more frequent in the complete placenta previa group.

Table 3: Pregnancy Outcomes by Placenta Previa Type

Outcome	Complete (n=30)	Partial (n=25)	Marginal (n=20)	Low-lying (n=25)	Total (n=100)
Cesarean Section	30 (100%)	21 (84%)	13 (65%)	15 (60%)	78 (78%)
Vaginal Delivery	0 (0%)	4 (16%)	7 (35%)	10 (40%)	22 (22%)
Mean Gestational Age (weeks)	35.0 $\pm$ 2.0	36.0 $\pm$ 2.3	36.8 $\pm$ 2.0	36.5 $\pm$ 2.5	36.1 $\pm$ 2.4
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.6 $\pm$ 0.4	2.8 $\pm$ 0.5	3.1 $\pm$ 0.4	3.0 $\pm$ 0.5	2.9 $\pm$ 0.5
Mean 5-minute Apgar Score	7.8 $\pm$ 1.4	8.2 $\pm$ 1.3	8.9 $\pm$ 1.0	8.8 $\pm$ 1.1	8.5 $\pm$ 1.2

Maternal and Neonatal Complications

- **Maternal Complications:** Maternal complications were observed in 35% of the participants. The most common complications were postpartum hemorrhage (15%), need for blood transfusion (12%), and prolonged hospital stay (8%). Maternal complications were significantly more frequent in the complete placenta previa group ($p < 0.05$).

- **Neonatal Complications:** Neonatal complications occurred in 25% of the cases, with preterm birth (18%) and low birth weight (10%) being the most common. Neonatal complications were more common in the complete and partial placenta previa groups ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Maternal and Neonatal Complications by Placenta Previa Type

Complication	Complete (n=30)	Partial (n=25)	Marginal (n=20)	Low-lying (n=25)	Total (n=100)
Maternal Complications	18 (60%)	9 (36%)	4 (20%)	4 (16%)	35 (35%)
Postpartum Hemorrhage	9 (30%)	4 (16%)	1 (5%)	1 (4%)	15 (15%)
Blood Transfusion	7 (23%)	3 (12%)	1 (5%)	1 (4%)	12 (12%)
Prolonged Hospital Stay	2 (7%)	2 (8%)	1 (5%)	3 (12%)	8 (8%)
Neonatal Complications	15 (50%)	7 (28%)	2 (10%)	1 (4%)	25 (25%)
Preterm Birth	12 (40%)	4 (16%)	1 (5%)	1 (4%)	18 (18%)
Low Birth Weight	6 (20%)	3 (12%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	10 (10%)

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between placenta previa type and several pregnancy outcomes, including mode of delivery, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, Apgar scores, and both maternal and

neonatal complications. Complete placenta previa was associated with a higher risk of cesarean delivery, preterm birth, lower birth weight, and maternal and neonatal complications ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Summary of Statistical Significance

Outcome	p-value
Mode of Delivery	<0.001
Gestational Age at Delivery	0.005
Birth Weight	0.002
5-minute Apgar Score	0.018
Maternal Complications	<0.001
Neonatal Complications	0.010

Discussion

The findings revealed that the type of placenta previa significantly influences both maternal and neonatal outcomes. Specifically, complete placenta previa was associated with the highest risk of adverse outcomes, including a 100% rate of cesarean delivery, earlier gestational age at delivery, lower birth weight, and lower Apgar scores compared to other types of placenta previa.

Participants with complete placenta previa had a mean gestational age at delivery of 35.0 weeks, significantly earlier than those with other types of placenta previa, which likely contributed to the lower mean birth weight of 2.6 kg in this group. This earlier delivery and lower birth weight also correlated with a higher incidence of neonatal complications, such as preterm birth and low birth weight, emphasizing the increased vulnerability of infants born to mothers with complete placenta previa.

Maternal complications were also more frequent among women with complete placenta previa, with a 60% complication rate, including postpartum hemorrhage and the need for blood transfusions. This group also exhibited a higher frequency of prolonged hospital stays, reflecting the more severe clinical management required.

Overall, the study underscores the critical need for targeted management strategies in pregnancies complicated by complete placenta previa to mitigate the risks of adverse outcomes for both the mother and the neonate. The significant associations between placenta previa type and pregnancy outcomes suggest that early identification and close monitoring of these cases are essential to improve clinical outcomes.

Numerous researches have examined the impact of placenta previa position on the course of pregnancy, with an emphasis on the distinctions between anterior and posterior placental attachment. In a retrospective research it was found that the placental attachment location significantly

influenced pregnancy outcomes. Compared to placentation on the lateral or posterior walls, they discovered that anterior wall placentation was linked to shorter gestational age, lower birth weight, greater prenatal bleeding, and higher risks of postpartum haemorrhage. Furthermore, the research revealed anterior placental attachment to be a separate risk factor for postpartum haemorrhage, emphasising the need for greater caution in these situations [7].

In a comparable way, it was investigated the connection between pregnancy outcomes and the location of the placenta previa. Their research showed that, in contrast to posterior placenta previa, anterior placenta previa was linked to a greater frequency of preterm labour and unfavourable mother outcomes. Because there is a higher risk of morbidity for both the mother and the foetus in pregnancies with anterior placenta previa, the authors stressed the need of raising awareness and monitoring these pregnancies [8].

Further evidence for these conclusions came from a more recent study which demonstrated that placental attachment to the anterior wall was associated with unfavourable outcomes like low birth weight, increased postpartum haemorrhage, and a higher risk of needing a hysterectomy in comparison to cases with lateral or posterior placental attachment. According to this investigation supported the idea that anterior placentation has a number of serious concerns that need to be closely monitored during pregnancy [9].

Conclusion

The study found that the location of placenta previa significantly impacts pregnancy outcomes. Complete placenta previa was associated with a higher risk of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. This highlights the importance of careful monitoring and management of pregnancies complicated by placenta previa to optimize maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

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